

Monitoring Changes in Vitamin D Levels During the COVID-19 Pandemic with Routinely-Collected Laboratory Data

Authors: Lea Skapetze¹², Daniela Koller¹, Andreas Zwergal³⁴, Stefan Feuerriegel⁵⁶, Anna Rubinski^{2†}, Eva Grill^{14†}

Affiliations:

1 Institute for Medical Information Processing, Biometry, and Epidemiology, LMU Munich, Germany

2 Health Data Technologies GmbH (“Honic”), Neckarsulm, Germany

3 Department of Neurology, LMU University Hospital, LMU Munich, Germany

4 German Center for Vertigo and Balance Disorders (DSGZ), LMU University Hospital, LMU Munich, Germany

5 LMU Munich School of Management, LMU Munich, Germany

6 Munich Center for Machine Learning, Germany

† Senior authors

OBJECTIVES: Vitamin D plays a key role in bone health and immune regulation. The COVID-19 pandemic, with its lockdowns and limited outdoor exposure, raised concerns about widespread declines in vitamin D levels. This study aimed to examine changes in vitamin D levels and deficiency rates during the pandemic using routinely-collected laboratory data.

METHODS: We conducted a retrospective, observational study using real-world data from the Honic platform, sourced from laboratory information systems across Bavaria, Germany. Adults (≥ 18 years) with at least one 25-OH-vitamin D test between March 2018 and February 2022 were included. Patients were stratified into pre-pandemic (03/2018–02/2020) and pandemic (03/2020–02/2022) groups. Descriptive statistics, propensity score matching (PSM), and causal forest models were applied to assess adjusted changes in vitamin D levels and deficiency rates (< 20 $\mu\text{g/L}$), accounting for confounders like age, gender, and season.

RESULTS: The final sample included 292,187 patients (153,829 pre-pandemic; 138,358 during the pandemic). Mean vitamin D levels declined from 26.7 $\mu\text{g/L}$ to 26.0 $\mu\text{g/L}$ ($p < 0.001$), with deficiency rates rising from 31.2% to 35.2% ($p < 0.001$). Adjusted analyses

confirmed a significant reduction (-0.5 to -0.7 $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$) in mean levels and a 3–4 percentage point increase in deficiency rates. Declines were most pronounced in elderly women and during spring. Seasonal variation explained over 70% of observed heterogeneity.

CONCLUSIONS: Our findings highlight a population-wide decline in vitamin D levels during the COVID-19 pandemic, particularly among elderly women. The study demonstrates the value of real-world laboratory data for nutrient monitoring and underscores the importance of public health strategies to address deficiencies during periods of reduced sun exposure.